
HENRI: A DOMAIN-SPECIFIC LANGUAGE FOR REAL-TIME SOUND SYNTHESIS AS DYNAMICAL-SYSTEMS SIMULATION

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ABSTRACT

henri is a domain-specific programming language for real-time sound synthesis in which the fundamental abstraction is the dynamical system: a named piece of mutable state together with the ordinary differential equations that govern its evolution over time. Sound is produced by numerically integrating these systems at the audio sample rate using a symmetric symplectic splitting scheme, with oversampling for higher accuracy. An implicit midpoint integrator with Newton–Raphson iteration is additionally available for stiff systems—most notably for virtual-analog filter design with high resonance, where explicit schemes are unstable. The compute loop is JIT-compiled to native code via LLVM ORC JIT v3. *henri* can be used interactively through a REPL for experimentation and rapid prototyping, or as a compiler producing standalone executables, Pure Data externals, SuperCollider UGens, and WebAssembly modules. This report describes the core of the language, its numerical implementation, and its compilation targets. It is intended as a citable reference from papers that use the language for compositional and artistic work.

Keywords sound synthesis · dynamical systems · domain-specific language · symplectic integration · real-time audio · LLVM JIT compilation

1 Introduction

henri is a domain-specific programming language for real-time sound synthesis. Its name refers to Henri Poincaré, whose geometrical approach to the analysis of dynamical systems—the study of *flows* in *phase space*—provides the conceptual foundation of the language. In *henri*, the fundamental entities are called *flows*: named state variables whose evolution over time is specified by writing down their derivatives. This terminology is not metaphorical; it is drawn directly from the language of phase-space analysis, where a flow ϕ_t maps an initial condition to the state it evolves to at time t under a given system of differential equations.

The design choice that distinguishes *henri* from other audio programming environments is the commitment to making the dynamical system the *only* organising abstraction. Oscillators are coupled ODEs; filters are coupled ODEs; envelopes are coupled ODEs; networks of adaptive oscillators are still coupled ODEs. There is no separate oscillator abstraction, no separate filter abstraction, and no “unit generator” concept. Sound is produced by numerically integrating the equations at the audio sample rate.

This commitment is not purely technical; it is also an *aesthetic experiment*. Any programming language carries a specific understanding of the world—a set of assumptions about what the fundamental entities are and how they relate. This understanding shapes how the programmer formulates problems and, in the context of sound synthesis, what kinds of sonic results feel natural or accessible within the language. Most existing computer music languages inherit their organising metaphors from signal processing (unit generators, signal flow graphs, sample buffers) or from functional programming (pure functions, referential transparency). These metaphors are productive but they also carry a specific aesthetic: they privilege modularity, signal independence, and input–output separation, and they can present resistance to formulations that emphasise coupling, mutual influence, and emergence.

henri is an attempt to reverse this direction: to start from how the author understands sound synthesis—as the simulation of coupled dynamical systems—and to construct a language that reflects this understanding rather than requiring the user to work around the assumptions of an existing tool. It is therefore not a universal language but an idiosyncratic one, carrying a strong trace of the author’s mathematical, physical, and aesthetic background. Whether this idiosyncrasy is a limitation or a productive constraint is an open question that the author’s ongoing artistic practice is intended to test.

The language originated in, and continues to be driven by, the author’s artistic practice at the Institute of Electronic Music and Acoustics (IEM) in Graz. It is in continuous use for concert and installation work, including feedback performances and multi-year ensemble practice. This report provides a short reference to the core of the language, its numerical implementation, and its compilation targets. A more comprehensive treatment of the language and its design is planned separately; the in-repository documentation (a quick-start guide, a cheat sheet, and a full language reference) supplements this report.

henri can be used in two modes. In *REPL mode*, the user types definitions and expressions interactively; each definition is JIT-compiled and takes effect immediately in the running audio callback. This mode is the primary workflow—it allows rapid experimentation, live modification of running patches, and immediate sonic feedback. In *compiler mode*, a `.hr` source file is compiled to a standalone artefact (shared library, executable, plugin, or WebAssembly module) for deployment without the interactive environment.

The language is available under a free software licence at <https://git.iem.at/davidpirro/henri>. It has been developed and tested on Debian GNU/Linux on x86_64.

2 Core concepts

What a *henri* program denotes

A *henri* program denotes a system of ordinary differential equations together with the schedule by which they are integrated and the I/O ports through which they exchange information with the world. There is no other abstraction. Every named entity in the language is a piece of state with an evolution rule; every operator either constructs such state, specifies an evolution rule, or reads from existing state. A *henri* source file, taken as a whole, is the description of a vector field on a finite-dimensional state space, the choice of initial condition, the numerical scheme by which the state is advanced in time, and a mapping from the state to the audio output channels. This is the semantic foundation of the language and the source of the design choices documented in the remainder of this section.

2.1 Flows

The fundamental entity in *henri* is the *flow*. A flow is a named piece of state, scalar or vector-valued, that the compute function reads and writes once per audio sample. Flows are declared with the keyword `def`; the optional shape parameter declares a vector or shaped-array flow, and the optional parenthesised parameter declares a memory depth:

Listing 1: Flow declarations.

```
def x                # scalar flow
def v[4]            # four-element vector flow
def m[3,4]          # 3x4 shaped array flow (12 elements)
def x(256)          # scalar with 256 samples of history
def v[4](256)       # vector flow with memory
```

A scalar flow holds a single double-precision value; a vector flow holds an array of doubles whose length is fixed at compile time; a shaped-array flow preserves its shape under arithmetic and function application. Memory depth gives the flow a circular buffer of past values accessible through negative shifts (`x(-1)`, `x(-100)`). Internally the buffer length is rounded up to the next power of two so that the shift arithmetic compiles to a bit-mask. All shape and depth information is known statically; out-of-shape assignments are caught at code generation rather than at run-time.

The choice to make flows the only carrier of state—rather than introducing a separate “variable” or “signal” concept—is deliberate. A flow’s identity in *henri* is its trajectory through state space, and that trajectory is the object the rest of the language operates on. Reading a flow returns its current state; assigning to a flow sets that state directly; specifying a derivative tells the compute loop how to advance it.

2.2 Derivatives and integration

The operation that distinguishes *henri* from a pure signal-flow language is the specification of a derivative, written $f'()$. When the parser encounters a derivative definition, it adds the flow to the set of state variables that the compute loop integrates at audio rate using the symplectic splitting method described in Section 3:

Listing 2: A simple derivative.

```
def x
x'() = 1.0      # dx/dt = 1
x = 0          # initial condition

x()           # 0.000023 (after one sample at 44100 Hz)
```

After this, successive reads of $x()$ return increasing values: x is being integrated. The integration step is $\Delta t = 1/f_s$ where f_s is the audio sample rate, so a constant derivative of 1.0 means a state increment of about 2.27×10^{-5} per sample at 44.1 kHz; after one second of integration the state of x has reached the value 1.0. Reading the flow's value at any point returns its current state in this trajectory; the state is a real continuous quantity, sampled discretely.

The canonical example is the harmonic oscillator. The second-order Newtonian equation $m\ddot{x} = -kx$ becomes, on substituting $v = \dot{x}$ and $\omega^2 = k/m$, the system of two coupled first-order ODEs

$$\dot{x} = v, \quad \dot{v} = -\omega^2 x.$$

In *henri*, this is written directly as those two equations, scaled so that `self[0]` and `self[1]` play the roles of x and v :

Listing 3: Harmonic oscillator.

```
def osc[2]
osc[0]'() = -w * self[1]
osc[1]'() = w * self[0]
osc[0] = 0.5      # initial condition
```

This is the central commitment of the language: the semantic identity between “harmonic oscillator” and “two coupled ODEs” is taken seriously, and there is no separate oscillator abstraction into which the equations are poured. The oscillation is a property of the coupling between the two equations, not a primitive of the language. The keyword `self` inside a derivative refers to the flow being defined; `self[1]` is the second element of the flow's own state vector.

A typical pitfall for new users is to forget the initial condition: a system whose state begins at zero and whose derivative is also zero remains at zero forever. Setting an initial condition is the act of perturbing the system off the trivial solution and watching what the equations do.

2.3 Function definitions

A flow may also be given a *function definition* that sets its value directly each sample, without integration:

Listing 4: Function definition.

```
def y
y() = sin(2 * pi * 440 * t)
```

Here `t` is a built-in flow that holds the current time in seconds; `y` is updated each sample with the value of the right-hand side. Function definitions are the right tool when the result is a direct expression of the system's current state rather than the time-integral of a rate: discrete-time updates, feedback read-back from delay lines, output mixing, or any computation that does not need to accumulate over time.

A single flow may have both a function definition and a derivative definition, in which case the function is applied after the derivative integration step (see Section 2.6). This composite behaviour is used, for instance, for hard-clipping or saturating non-linearities applied to integrated state.

2.4 Memory access

A flow with declared memory depth can be read at past offsets:

Listing 5: Memory access.

```
def x(1024)
  x(-1)           # one sample ago
  x(-256)        # 256 samples ago
  x([-3..0])     # vector of the last four values
```

The negative shift specifies the offset in samples; positive shifts are an error. The memory buffer is circular and implemented as a flat array of double-precision values; the power-of-two rounding mentioned in Section 2.1 allows the read offset to be computed as a single bit-mask operation rather than a modulo. This is the interface used for delay lines, comb filters, and any operation that depends on a short history of the flow. For long delays (more than a few hundred samples), the same interface remains efficient; the memory cost is one double per declared sample of depth.

2.5 defconstant: reusable templates

A `defconstant` declares a *template*: a flow-like entity whose derivatives and function definitions are not integrated into the audio loop directly, but whose definitions are macro-expanded at each call site. Templates are the mechanism by which oscillators, filters, and other recurring patterns are factored out without the runtime cost of a function call:

Listing 6: A reusable oscillator template.

```
defconstant myosc[2]
  myosc[0]'(freq) = freq * self[1]
  myosc[1]'(freq) = -freq * self[0]

def o[2]
  o[j]'() = myosc[j]'(440 * pi2)
  o[0] = 0.5
```

When the template `myosc` is applied to the target flow `o`, the `self` keyword in the template is automatically rebound to `o`, and the index variable `j` is expanded over the target's first dimension. Each call site produces an independent set of integrated equations; two flows defined from the same template share no state. The mechanism is purely syntactic and operates at code-generation time, so templates have no runtime overhead beyond the equations they expand into.

The design rationale is that templates allow a library of reusable patterns—oscillators, integrators, simple filters—to be written without introducing function-call indirection at the audio rate. The in-repository standard library, loaded automatically at REPL start-up, contains roughly thirty such templates.

2.6 The compute loop

At audio rate, *henri* evaluates a single compiled *compute function* once per sample. The structure of this function is shown in Figure 1. The function takes as input the current values of all I/O flows (`in`, `midi`, `params`) and the current time, and produces as output the updated values of all flow state arrays plus the audio output buffer.

The compute function is regenerated whenever a definition is added or changed. Each regeneration performs the same procedure: the dependency graph of all flow definitions is analysed statically, the integrated flows and the function-defined flows are separated, and a per-sample compute body is emitted that proceeds in two passes. The first pass advances every integrated flow by one step (sub-stepped according to the active oversampling factor). The second pass evaluates every function-defined flow in topological order on the dependency graph, so that each flow's right-hand side reads the already-updated values of the flows it depends on.

The order in which definitions appear in the source is, in general, *not* the order in which the compute function evaluates them. Source order matters only for resolving redefinitions; the runtime ordering follows the dependency graph. A short example makes the distinction concrete:

Figure 1: Structure of the per-sample compute function. State arrays are read into local registers, derivatives are evaluated per flow (sub-stepped at the active oversampling factor), one symplectic integration step is taken, and function definitions are evaluated in dependency order before the result is written back to state arrays and to the audio output buffer.

Listing 7: Source order vs. evaluation order.

```

def x
def a
def b
a() = b * 2.0      # a reads b
b() = sin(t)      # b reads t (built-in)
x'() = a          # x integrates a
    
```

Although `a` is defined before `b` in the source, the compute function evaluates them in the opposite order: at each sample, the first pass integrates `x` using the current value of `a`; the second pass then evaluates `b` (which depends only on `t`), then `a` (which depends on `b`). The integration of `x` in the first pass therefore uses the value of `a` from the *previous* sample, while the assignment to `a` in the second pass uses `b` as updated this sample. This one-sample lag for derivative evaluation is a property of the two-pass structure and is consistent with how the symplectic integrator handles state-dependent forcing: derivatives are evaluated against the state that exists at the start of the integration step.

There is no runtime dispatch and no dynamic memory allocation; a typical compute function for a patch with a few dozen integrated flows compiles to a few hundred native instructions and executes in a few microseconds per sample on commodity hardware.

3 Numerical implementation

Sound synthesis at audio rate is numerically demanding. Direct application of standard explicit schemes (forward Euler, non-energy-preserving Runge–Kutta) introduces systematic energy drift in oscillator systems, which manifests audibly as amplitude blow-up, artificial decay, or outright numerical instability. For this reason, *henri* uses a symplectic integration scheme as its default [Strang, 1968, Hairer et al., 2006, Pirrò, 2018].

3.1 Hamiltonian systems and symplecticity

The systems dealt with in *henri* are, in the general case, systems of coupled differential equations. Many of them—oscillators, conservative mechanical models, spring-mass networks—belong to the important class of *Hamiltonian systems*, described by a Hamiltonian function

$$H(q, p) = T(p) + U(q), \quad (1)$$

where q and p are generalised position and momentum coordinates, $T(p)$ is the kinetic energy, and $U(q)$ the potential energy. The time evolution is governed by Hamilton’s equations:

$$\dot{p} = -\frac{\partial H}{\partial q}, \quad \dot{q} = \frac{\partial H}{\partial p}. \quad (2)$$

The phase space spanned by (q, p) is the space in which the system’s trajectory unfolds. To any Hamiltonian corresponds a *flow* $\phi_t : (q_0, p_0) \mapsto (q(t), p(t))$, which is a *symplectic map*: it preserves the area of any region in phase space. This area-preservation property is intimately related to the conservation of energy and to Liouville’s theorem. The numerical methods used in *henri* are chosen to respect this property.

3.2 Symplectic Euler and the splitting idea

The simplest symplectic integrator is the *symplectic Euler* method. For a separable Hamiltonian with $-\partial H/\partial q = f(q)$ (the force) and $\partial H/\partial p = p/m = v$ (the velocity), it takes the form:

$$p_{n+1} = p_n + h f(q_n), \quad (3)$$

$$q_{n+1} = q_n + \frac{h}{m} p_{n+1}, \quad (4)$$

where h is the time step. Each variable uses the *updated* value of the other: the momentum is advanced explicitly, then the position uses the new momentum implicitly. This asymmetry is what makes the method symplectic—it preserves the phase-space area at each step, unlike forward or backward Euler alone.

This method can be understood as the *composition* of two simpler flows, each acting along one dimension of phase space:

$$\phi_h^{[1]} : \quad q_{n+1} = q_n, \quad p_{n+1} = p_n + h f(q_n), \quad (5)$$

$$\phi_h^{[2]} : \quad q_{n+1} = q_n + \frac{h}{m} p_n, \quad p_{n+1} = p_n, \quad (6)$$

so that one step of the symplectic Euler is $\Phi_h = \phi_h^{[1]} \circ \phi_h^{[2]}$.

3.3 Symmetric splitting: the Störmer–Verlet method

The default integrator in *henri* is built from three principles [Hairer et al., 2006, Pirrò, 2018]:

- **Splitting:** a flow in phase space is decomposed into the composition of simpler flows, each acting along one dimension.
- **Symmetry:** the *adjoint* of a method Φ_h is defined as $\Phi_h^* = \Phi_{-h}^{-1}$ (the method run backward in time). A method is *symmetric* if $\Phi_h^* = \Phi_h$. Symmetry is related to the time-reversibility of conservative systems.
- **Composition:** if Φ_h and Ψ_h are methods of order r and s , their composition $\Phi_{h/2} \circ \Psi_{h/2}$ is a method of order $r + s$.

Composing the symplectic Euler with its adjoint at half-steps yields a *symmetric* method of second order. For the two-dimensional case this gives the Störmer–Verlet scheme:

$$q_{n+\frac{1}{2}} = q_n + \frac{h}{2m} p_n, \quad (7)$$

$$p_{n+1} = p_n + h f(q_{n+\frac{1}{2}}), \quad (8)$$

$$q_{n+1} = q_{n+\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{h}{2m} p_{n+1}. \quad (9)$$

The palindromic structure—half-step, full step, half-step—is the hallmark of symmetric splitting methods.

3.4 Generalisation to n dimensions

For an n -dimensional system $\dot{x}_i = f_i(x_1, \dots, x_n)$, the total flow Φ_h is split into n first-order flows:

$$\Phi_h = \phi_h^1 \circ \phi_h^2 \circ \dots \circ \phi_h^n, \quad (10)$$

where each ϕ_h^i advances the i -th state variable by one step while holding the others at their current values. A second-order symmetric method is then:

$$\Phi_{h/2}^* \circ \Phi_{h/2} = \phi_{h/2}^n \circ \dots \circ \phi_{h/2}^1 \circ \phi_{h/2}^1 \circ \dots \circ \phi_{h/2}^n. \quad (11)$$

This is the integration method used in *henri* [Pirrò, 2018] for arbitrary multi-dimensional dynamical systems. Higher-order methods can be obtained by reapplying composition:

$$\Phi_{h/4}^* \circ \Phi_{h/4} \circ \Phi_{h/4}^* \circ \Phi_{h/4} \quad (12)$$

yields a fourth-order symmetric symplectic scheme [Hairer et al., 2006].

3.5 Oversampling

In practice, the default strategy in *henri* for achieving higher accuracy is *oversampling*: subdividing the audio sample interval into k substeps and applying the second-order symmetric splitting at the reduced step size h/k . The error scales as $O(h^2/k^2)$, so doubling the oversampling factor reduces the integration error by a factor of four.

By default, *henri* uses two substeps per sample. The oversampling factor can be set globally or per-flow, allowing the user to allocate computational resources where they are most needed (e.g., high-frequency oscillators, stiff resonant filters) while leaving less demanding subsystems at the default rate.

3.6 Implicit integration for stiff systems

For stiff systems—in particular for high-frequency resonant filters and tightly coupled networks where even high oversampling factors are insufficient—*henri* additionally provides an *implicit midpoint rule* solved by a full Newton–Raphson iteration. The implicit midpoint advances the state as:

$$x_{n+1} = x_n + h f\left(\frac{x_n + x_{n+1}}{2}\right), \quad (13)$$

which is an implicit equation in x_{n+1} , solved iteratively by Newton–Raphson. Writing $R(x_{k+1}) = x_{k+1} - x_n - h f(\bar{x})$ for the residual and $\bar{x} = (x_n + x_{k+1})/2$ for the midpoint, the Newton update at iteration k is

$$M \delta = -R(x_k), \quad M = I - \frac{h}{2} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \Big|_{\bar{x}}, \quad x_{k+1} = x_k + \delta,$$

where M is the Jacobian of the residual at the midpoint. The iteration starts from $x_0 = x_n$ and terminates when the relative correction $\max_i |\delta_i| / (|x_{k+1,i}| + \varepsilon)$ falls below a user-specified tolerance, or when a fixed maximum number of iterations (default seven) is reached. The Jacobian M is assembled by finite differences at code-generation time, and the resulting linear system is solved by Gaussian elimination unrolled for the size of the local subsystem. The implicit midpoint scheme is both symplectic and A-stable, combining energy preservation with unconditional numerical stability. It is activated per-flow with a tolerance argument that maps directly to the convergence criterion above:

Listing 8: Switching a flow to the implicit midpoint integrator.

```
setImplicit(filter, 0.001) # 0.1% relative convergence
```

The principal application in audio is virtual-analog (VA) filter design, where high- Q resonant peaks at frequencies close to the Nyquist rate produce systems whose linear stability bound under explicit integration becomes prohibitively small. The state-variable filter (SVF) is a familiar example. With $\omega = 2\pi f_c$ the angular cutoff frequency and ζ a damping factor (low ζ corresponds to high resonance), the SVF is the two-dimensional driven system:

$$\dot{x}(t) = \omega y(t), \quad (14)$$

$$\dot{y}(t) = -\omega x(t) - 2\zeta\omega y(t) + \omega u(t), \quad (15)$$

where x is the lowpass output, y the bandpass driver, and u the input. As ζ decreases (resonance increases), the spectrum of the system’s Jacobian moves close to the imaginary axis, and explicit integration requires impractically small step sizes to stay stable. Under the implicit midpoint scheme the system remains stable for arbitrary $\zeta > 0$ and for ω up to (and slightly beyond) the Nyquist rate. In *henri*, the filter is written directly as the equations, in roughly a dozen lines of code; the full patch is shown in Appendix A as Listing 17.

The corresponding LLVM IR is qualitatively different from the explicit case shown in Section 3.7: per audio sample, the JIT-generated loop assembles a numerical Jacobian by perturbing each state variable, builds the residual $x_{n+1} - x_n - h f(\bar{x})$ at the midpoint $\bar{x} = (x_n + x_{n+1})/2$, solves the resulting linear system by Gaussian elimination unrolled at the size of the local subsystem (here 2×2), and updates x_{n+1} until the relative correction falls below the tolerance specified to `setImplicit()`. The loop typically converges in two or three iterations on smooth signals and may take more on transients; the iteration count and convergence test are emitted as native code. The full annotated IR is given in Appendix A as Listing 19.

The per-sample cost of the implicit integrator is roughly an order of magnitude higher than the explicit case, which is why the choice of scheme is per-flow opt-in through `setImplicit()` rather than the default. The trade-off is: explicit integration is cheap and unconditionally stable only at small step sizes; implicit integration is more expensive per step but stable at any step size for stiff problems. *henri* makes both available so that a single patch can use the cheap scheme for the easy parts of its dynamics and the more expensive scheme only for the specific subsystems that need it.

3.7 JIT compilation via LLVM

The compute function is not interpreted. *henri* generates LLVM intermediate representation (IR) for each definition and JIT-compile the resulting module via ORC JIT v3, producing native x86_64 code. The compilation pipeline proceeds in five stages. The parser produces an abstract syntax tree from the source text. A pre-codegen pass walks the tree to resolve variable references, expand free indices, and substitute templates. A code-generation pass emits LLVM IR for each flow’s compute logic, attaching shape metadata and loop- vectorisation hints. An optimisation pass applies a sequence of standard transformations available in the LLVM optimisation pipeline: SROA (scalar replacement of aggregates), loop fusion, GVN (global value numbering), dead-store elimination, instruction combination, and forced 4-wide loop vectorisation on x86_64 with libmvec for the transcendental functions. Finally, the optimised module is handed to the JIT for native code generation and linked into the running audio callback.

The IR-level effect is best seen on a small example. Listing 18 (in Appendix A) shows representative LLVM IR generated for the harmonic oscillator of Listing 3 after optimisation. The structure of that IR reflects, almost line for line, the mathematical structure of the integrator: three sub-steps—a half-step on the position-like coordinate, a full step on the momentum-like coordinate using the updated position, and a second half-step on the position—arranged in the palindromic pattern characteristic of the symmetric symplectic splitting of Section 3.3. The factor of $2 \cdot 10^3$ in the middle step versus $1 \cdot 10^3$ in the half-steps is precisely the Δt versus $\Delta t/2$ structure of the scheme. The two coupled ODEs of Listing 3 have been compiled to roughly a dozen native floating-point instructions per audio sample.

In REPL mode, the time from a typed definition to its running in the audio thread is on the order of tens of milliseconds, which makes live coding practical: a definition is typed, compiled, optimised, and linked into the running audio callback before the next audio buffer is filled, so the change is audible essentially immediately.

4 Worked examples

The three examples below illustrate, in increasing order of sonic ambition, what *henri* programs look like and what each example demonstrates about the language. They are not presented as instruments to be deployed but as minimal cases that exercise specific features: derivative-based oscillation, compile-time index expansion, and the use of an arbitrary mathematical model as a sound generator.

4.1 A damped harmonic oscillator

The damped harmonic oscillator at angular frequency $\omega = 2\pi \cdot 440$ rad/s with damping coefficient $\gamma = 2.0$ is described by the system of two coupled first-order ODEs:

$$\dot{x}(t) = \omega y(t) - \gamma x(t), \quad (16)$$

$$\dot{y}(t) = -\omega x(t) - \gamma y(t). \quad (17)$$

In phase space, the trajectory of (x, y) is a logarithmic spiral converging on the origin, the rate of convergence set by γ . The corresponding *henri* program is a direct transliteration:

Listing 9: Damped harmonic oscillator at 440 Hz.

```
def osc[2]
def gamma          # damping coefficient
gamma = 2.0
osc[0]'() = 440 * pi2 * self[1] - gamma * self[0]
osc[1]'() = -440 * pi2 * self[0] - gamma * self[1]
osc[0] = 0.5
out[0]() = osc[0] * 0.1
out[1]() = osc[1] * 0.1
```

Setting an initial condition (`osc[0] = 0.5`) plucks the oscillator: the state begins at the point $(0.5, 0)$ in phase space and follows the spiral inward until it returns to the origin (Figure 2).

The audio output is a 440 Hz sine tone whose amplitude decays exponentially with time constant $1/\gamma = 0.5$ seconds. The example is short, but four features of *henri* are visible in it. First, the oscillator is written as its actual ODE system, not as a call to a `Sine.ar` or equivalent unit generator. Second, the `self` keyword refers to the oscillator’s own state vector. Third, the output is written by assigning to the built-in `out` flow, which carries audio to the audio device. Fourth, the system is plucked by an explicit assignment to its initial condition; without that assignment the equations have the trivial solution $(0, 0)$ and the oscillator stays silent.

Figure 2: Phase portrait of the damped harmonic oscillator of Listing 9. The state (x, y) begins at $(0.5, 0)$ and spirals inward toward the origin; the rate of inward contraction is set by the damping coefficient $\gamma = 2.0$ in the equations. The audio output is the projection $x(t)$ onto the horizontal axis.

4.2 A bank of harmonic oscillators

The example above generalises naturally to a bank of N independent oscillators with frequencies $\omega_i = 2\pi \cdot f_i$, $i \in \{0, \dots, N-1\}$, summed to a single output channel:

$$\dot{x}_i(t) = \omega_i y_i(t), \quad \dot{y}_i(t) = -\omega_i x_i(t), \quad y_{\text{out}}(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \frac{x_i(t)}{i+1}. \quad (18)$$

For $N = 8$ and $f_i = 100(i+1)$ Hz, this produces additive synthesis of a fundamental at 100 Hz with seven harmonics weighted at $1/i$:

Listing 10: Bank of eight harmonic oscillators at $f_i = 100(i+1)$ Hz.

```
def bank[8, 2]
def freq[8]
freq = [100 * i for i in 1..8] * pi2

bank[i, 0]'() = freq[i] * self[i, 1]
bank[i, 1]'() = -freq[i] * self[i, 0]
bank[0..7, 0] = 0.3

out[0]() = sum([bank[k,0] / (k+1) for k in 0..7]) * 0.05
```

The construct `bank[i, 0]'()` uses a free index `i` on the left-hand side. *henri* expands such free indices at compile time: the parser recognises that `i` is unbound in the surrounding scope and replicates the equation once per value of `i` in the first dimension of `bank`. The result is eight independent ODE pairs, each integrated separately, with no run-time loop overhead. The same expansion is used in the right-hand-side comprehension `[bank[k, 0] / (k+1) for k in 0..7]`, which produces a constant array of eight terms summed at compile time. The audible output is a saw-wave-like timbre of harmonics weighted toward the fundamental: the example illustrates that *henri*'s notion of “one ODE per sample” generalises without effort to “one ODE *per oscillator* per sample,” and that the resulting code is as concise as the equation that describes it.

4.3 A Lorenz attractor as sound source

The third example is the Lorenz system, the canonical three-variable chaotic ODE introduced by Edward Lorenz in 1963:

$$\dot{x}(t) = \sigma(y - x), \quad (19)$$

$$\dot{y}(t) = x(\rho - z) - y, \quad (20)$$

$$\dot{z}(t) = xy - \beta z, \quad (21)$$

Figure 3: Phase-space trajectory of the Lorenz system of Listing 11, rendered from *henri*'s offline output. The classical butterfly shape is visible; the trajectory winds densely around two unstable foci without ever repeating. The audio output is the projection of this trajectory onto a single coordinate; the irregular alternation between the two “wings” is what is heard as glitchy non-periodicity.

with classical parameters $\sigma = 10$, $\rho = 28$, $\beta = 8/3$. Trajectories of this system never repeat, never diverge, and never settle on a fixed point: they wind densely around a fractal set known as the Lorenz attractor. In *henri*:

Listing 11: Lorenz attractor as audio source.

```
def lz[3]
  lz[0]'() = 10.0 * (self[1] - self[0])
  lz[1]'() = self[0] * (28.0 - self[2]) - self[1]
  lz[2]'() = self[0] * self[1] - (8.0/3.0) * self[2]
  lz[0] = 0.1
  out[0]() = lz[0] * 0.02
```

The equations are transliterated from the textbook form with no adaptation for the audio-rate context other than the amplitude scaling on the output. Figure 3 shows a phase portrait of the resulting trajectory captured directly from the running *henri* REPL: *henri* ships with a small GTK oscilloscope window, the `scope`, which can be switched into a Lissajous (XY) display mode and which renders any flow's state in real time as the system evolves. The image shown is one such Lissajous capture of `lz[0]` versus `lz[1]` during a few seconds of integration. The resulting sound is glitchy and non-periodic, alternating between the two “wings” of the attractor at irregular intervals; the timescale of the alternation is set implicitly by the sample rate (because the equations have no explicit Δt , the integration step $1/f_s$ becomes the system's natural unit of time).

This example is in the report partly to demonstrate that the language's central commitment is not metaphorical: any system of ODEs can be a sound source, and a chaotic attractor written in standard form runs as audio without intermediate representation. A comparable patch in Faust would require either external state through delay lines or the use of an extension; in SuperCollider, the system would have to be written as a custom UGen in C++ or as a chain of `Integrator.ar` ugens with manual feedback. In *henri*, the integration is the default mode of operation.

4.4 Karplus–Strong: a memory-depth example

The three examples above all use the derivative mechanism. The fourth example uses the complementary mechanism—*memory depth*—to demonstrate that delay lines, comb filters, and similar history-dependent constructs are first-class in *henri* as well. The Karplus–Strong plucked-string algorithm [Karplus and Strong, 1983], in its simplest form, maintains a circular buffer of length N and updates each sample by averaging two adjacent past samples

and writing the result back, with a small attenuation per pass to simulate energy loss:

$$y(t) = \frac{1}{2}(y(t - \tau) + y(t - \tau - \Delta)), \quad \tau = N/f_s. \quad (22)$$

The averaging acts as a low-pass filter (each pass attenuates high frequencies more than low ones), and the buffer length N sets the perceived pitch at f_s/N . To start the system, the buffer is initialised with broadband noise; once the noise has recirculated a few times the buffer settles into a quasi-periodic waveform whose spectrum is determined by the filter's cumulative response. In *henri*:

Listing 12: Karplus–Strong plucked-string at $f_s/220 \approx 218$ Hz.

```
def excite
excite'() = -2000.0 * self      # short noise burst envelope
excite = 1.0                  # pluck

def y(2048)
y() = excite * noise() * 0.5 +
      0.499 * (y(-220) + y(-221))

out[0]() = y * 0.3
```

The flow y is declared with memory depth 2048, giving it a circular buffer of 2048 past values. The function definition assigns to $y()$ on every sample; the right-hand side combines an excitation term (broadband noise gated by a fast-decaying envelope) with the comb-filter feedback term that reads the buffer at offsets -220 and -221 . The multiplier 0.499 is just below 0.5 so the system is lossy and the resulting tone decays over a few seconds. On the first sample, $y(-220)$ and $y(-221)$ are zero (the buffer is initialised to zero); the noise burst writes the initial broadband content; subsequent samples mix the noise tail with the comb-filter recirculation; once the noise has decayed, the comb-filtered residue continues to recirculate until the 0.499 factor drains it. The broadband nature of the initial excitation is what gives the resulting tone its plucked-string character. The example illustrates that the same memory-depth interface used for short look-back operations ($x(-1)$ for differentiation, $x(-3..0)$ for short window operations) extends without modification to the delay lines that classical waveguide synthesis depends on.

4.5 A Kuramoto network of phase oscillators

The Kuramoto model is the canonical minimal description of synchronisation phenomena in coupled oscillator networks [Kuramoto, 1975, Pikovsky et al., 2001]. An ensemble of N phase oscillators with intrinsic frequencies f_i and global coupling strength K evolves according to

$$\dot{\theta}_i(t) = f_i + \frac{K}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \sin(\theta_j(t) - \theta_i(t)). \quad (23)$$

For K above a critical value K_c the oscillators synchronise into a coherent cluster; below K_c they drift independently. The transition is sharp and audible. In *henri*:

Listing 13: A Kuramoto network of eight phase oscillators with all-to-all coupling.

```
def ku[8]                                # phase oscillators
def freq[8]
freq = 100

ku[i] = randH() * pi2                   # initialise to random phases

def coup
coup = 0.5                              # coupling strength

ku[i]'() = freq[i] +
           (coup / 8) * sum([sin(self[j] - self[i])
                             for j in 0..7])
ku[i]() = self[i] % pi2                 # wrap phase into [0, 2*pi)

out[0]() = 0.5 * sum(ku) / (8 * pi2)    # sonify phase directly
```

The example combines features that no other example in this report uses jointly: a free-index expansion on the left-hand side (`ku[i]'`), a comprehension on the right-hand side that closes over a different index (`[... for j in 0..7]`), and a function definition on the same flow that wraps the phase into $[0, 2\pi)$ each sample. At code-generation time the construct is fully unrolled into eight derivative equations, each with seven coupling terms; the resulting compute function computes the synchronised or drifting collective behaviour at audio rate. Increasing `coup` interactively at the REPL moves the system across the synchronisation threshold K_c ; the sonic result—obtained here by sonifying the average phase directly—is a transition from incoherent drift into a single locked rhythm. Random phase initialisation via `randH()` ensures that the system explores its full state space rather than starting from a degenerate configuration.

5 Multiple time domains and compilation targets

5.1 Time domains

The default time domain in *henri* runs inside the audio callback at the audio sample rate, and is referred to by the built-in time variable `t`. Some patches benefit from additional rates—a control-rate envelope generator running at 1 kHz rather than 48 kHz, a slow modulator running at the visual frame rate, an ODE simulation needing a smaller step size than $1/f_s$ to remain numerically stable. The `deftime` construct introduces a named time domain with its own integration step, its own compute function, and its own execution backend:

Listing 14: Three alternative time domain backends.

```
deftime ctl : thread      # dedicated pthread
deftime fast : timer     # Linux timerfd
deftime audio2 : jack 2 2 # separate Jack client
```

A flow is bound to a particular time domain by naming that domain in the derivative declaration:

Listing 15: Binding flows to non-default time domains.

```
def env
env'(ctl) = -2.0 * self      # decays at control-rate ctl

def slowmod
slowmod'(fast) = 1.0        # ramps at the timer rate

def osc[2]                  # default time domain (audio rate)
osc[0]'() = -440 * pi2 * self[1]
osc[1]'() = 440 * pi2 * self[0]
```

The flow `env` evolves on the `ctl` thread, `slowmod` on the `fast` timer, and `osc` on the default audio callback (no explicit time argument). A flow's derivative or function definition can read state from a flow bound to a different time domain without any further syntactic ceremony: when the JIT generates the compute function for the reading flow's time domain, it detects that the source flow belongs to a different domain and inserts a relaxed atomic load to prevent tearing of the eight-byte read, without imposing acquire/release overhead. Each time domain's compute function is generated separately, so the per-callback work is local to that domain.

The four available backends are `callback` (the default, synchronous; the user advances time explicitly with `tick()`); `thread` (a dedicated pthread with `clock_nanosleep` scheduling, drift-free under absolute time); `timer` (a Linux `timerfd` with catch-up semantics on missed ticks); and `jack` (a separate Jack client with its own audio I/O ports).

The `deftime` mechanism is, at the time of writing, an experimental feature that has been used only sparingly in the author's own practice. The thread-safety guarantee provided is limited: cross-time reads are atomic at the level of single double-precision values, but no broader synchronisation mechanism (mutex, lock-free queue, generation counter) is exposed at the language level. Patches that share substantial state across time domains should be designed with this limitation in mind.

The practical effect is that control-rate envelopes, audio-rate oscillators, an independent audio stream on a second Jack client, and a real-time scheduling-priority subsystem can all coexist in a single program, each advancing on its own clock, without the user having to write any threading or synchronisation code. Cross-domain coupling—a flow in `ctl` read by an audio-rate flow—is permitted and handled by the atomic load mechanism mentioned above.

5.2 Compilation targets

Beyond the REPL, *henri* compiles `.hr` files to several deployable artefacts:

- a shared library (`libfoo.so`) for embedding in a host application via the C API;
- a standalone Jack client executable, runnable as a command-line tool that connects to a running Jack server;
- a Jack client with a GTK oscilloscope window for visual inspection of internal flows;
- a Pure Data external (`foo~.pd_linux`) usable as a signal-rate object inside Pd patches;
- a SuperCollider UGen (`Foo.so + Foo.sc`) that can be installed in the SC extensions directory and used as any other UGen in the SuperCollider language;
- a WebAssembly module for browser audio via `AudioWorklet`.

The Pure Data and SuperCollider targets allow a patch developed interactively in the *henri* REPL to be deployed into existing computer-music ecosystems without modification. The WebAssembly target reaches the browser; the C-library target reaches whatever host application can link a shared object. Each target is generated by combining the *henri*-compiled `henri_nat.o` with a small target-specific template that handles the host's I/O conventions.

For batch rendering and offline use, an `henri-batch` command-line tool produces raw audio, WAV16, WAV32, or WAV64 output from a `.hr` file at any sample rate, suitable for piping into standard audio tools or for use in scripted synthesis pipelines. An embeddable C library `libhenri-core.a`, with a minimal API (`henri_init`, `henri_eval`, `henri_compute`, `henri_register_function`, and state-access functions), is also provided for host programs that use *henri* as a simulation engine rather than as a standalone tool.

6 Related work

henri sits in a small ecosystem of domain-specific languages for real-time audio synthesis. The closest neighbours are Faust, SuperCollider, ChuckK, and Max/MSP's `gen~` subsystem. Faust [Orlarey et al., 2009] treats audio processing as functional programming over signals: a Faust program is a block-diagram expression in an algebra of five composition operators, and the compiler translates this expression into efficient C++. SuperCollider [McCartney, 2002] pairs a high-level synthesis language with a low-level synthesis server connected by Open Sound Control; new unit generators are added in C++. ChuckK [Wang and Cook, 2003] foregrounds time as a first-class language construct, with explicit “shreds” that advance time by samples or other units, and supports on-the-fly programming through its virtual-machine architecture. The `gen~` subsystem inside Max/MSP compiles small signal-flow graphs to native code at edit time, with a syntax close to Faust's but embedded in a visual patcher.

henri differs from these languages in one load-bearing respect: it commits to the dynamical-systems view as the *only* organising abstraction. Every entity the user meets is a system of ODEs (or, in the discrete case, a function definition that updates state once per sample), and the language provides no facility that stands outside this framing. There are no unit generators in *henri*, no busses, no signal-flow operators, no separate notion of audio versus control rate. This is restrictive in the obvious sense that some ways of describing sound that are natural in Faust or SuperCollider become awkward in *henri*; it is liberating in the less obvious sense that any ODE system that can be written down on paper can be run as audio without translation.

henri also differs from scientific-computing tools such as SciML, SUNDIALS, or `DifferentialEquations.jl`. Those libraries are designed for offline simulation of ODE systems of any size, with adaptive step-size control, error estimation, and long-running integration as first-order requirements; real-time audio constraints (constant per-sample compute time, audio-rate stability, low-latency JIT compilation, integration with the audio I/O stack) are not their concern. *henri* sits in the opposite corner of the design space: it accepts a restricted class of systems in exchange for the guarantees that audio rate demands. Three properties are characteristic and, to the author's knowledge, not jointly available elsewhere: the ODE-as-only-abstraction commitment; symplectic-by-default integration with optional implicit midpoint for stiff subsystems; and a REPL workflow in which a typed definition is running in the audio thread within tens of milliseconds.

7 Limitations and future work

henri is a research tool in continuous development, and its current state has known limits. Several of these are worth naming explicitly so that users and citing papers understand the scope.

Static state size. The state vector of every flow is fixed at compile time. There is no construct for dynamic-size arrays or for adding state during execution. A flow declared as `def x[8]` cannot become `def x[16]` at run-time without restarting the REPL or recompiling. This is a deliberate trade-off in service of real-time guarantees (no allocations in the audio callback, no dynamic dispatch, predictable per-sample compute time), but it means that some adaptive structures familiar from scientific computing—adding particles to a swarm, growing a network as the simulation evolves—are not directly expressible.

Single-thread audio. The default audio callback runs on a single thread. Multi-time domains (Section 5) provide parallelism through distinct callbacks (separate Jack clients, dedicated pthreads, timer-driven loops) but each individual compute function runs single-threaded. For very large patches—hundreds of integrated flows—this can become the bottleneck. Automatic parallelisation of a single compute function is currently not supported; the user must split the patch across time domains manually.

Limited platform support. *henri* is developed and tested on Debian GNU/Linux on x86_64. The WebAssembly compilation target works on any modern browser. macOS, Windows, and ARM/aarch64 builds are plausible but not part of the current release. The Jack audio server is required for the default audio backend; alternative backends (PortAudio, ALSA direct) are not yet implemented.

No formal type system. The language has no user-visible type system beyond shape checking. All numeric values are double-precision; there is no support for single-precision, integer-only, or fixed-point arithmetic, even though some target platforms (WebAssembly on mobile, embedded systems) would benefit from such control. The shape-checking that does exist is performed at code generation rather than as a separate type-checking phase, which means that some shape errors are caught later in the pipeline than would be ideal.

Documentation lag. The features documented in this report represent a stable subset of the language. Several more recent additions—parameterised module instantiation, automatic differentiation through `grad()`, the C library API for embedding—are present in the codebase but not described here. Subsequent versions of this report will fill those gaps.

Future work

Three directions are actively being pursued. First, the language’s commitment to ODE-as-only-abstraction has been tested largely on smooth dynamical systems; recent work extends it to networks of adaptive coupled oscillators (Hopf-type with Hebbian frequency learning) and to neural-network-like adaptive systems built from coupled differential equations rather than from discrete-time matrix multiplications. Second, the multi-time-domain machinery is being extended with support for stochastic time domains (event-driven rather than sample-rate-driven), which would allow MIDI-driven and event-driven systems to coexist with audio-rate flows on equal footing. Third, the symbolic differentiation infrastructure (`grad()`, `rhs()`, `jacobian()`) is being expanded to support sensitivity analysis of audio-rate ODE systems—making it possible to ask, in the language itself, what the derivative of a sound’s character is with respect to a parameter.

Acknowledgements

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8 Availability and how to cite

henri is available at <https://git.iem.at/davidpirro/henri> under a free software licence. The repository contains a full language reference at `doc/language-reference.md`, a cheat sheet at `doc/cheat-sheet.md`, a quick-start guide at `doc/quick-start.md`, and a library of examples in `examples/`. The standard library of reusable `defconstant` templates is loaded automatically at REPL start-up from `init/defs.hr`.

This report is deposited on Zenodo with DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20044047. To cite *henri*, use the BibTeX entry below; subsequent versions of the report will share a concept DOI that always resolves to the latest version.

Listing 16: BibTeX entry for citing this technical report.

```
@techreport{pirro2026henri,
  author      = {Pirr\`o, David},
  title       = {henri: A Domain-Specific Language for
                Real-Time Sound Synthesis as
                Dynamical-Systems Simulation},
  year        = {2026},
  institution = {Institute of Electronic Music and Acoustics,
                University of Music and Performing Arts Graz},
  doi         = {10.5281/zenodo.20044047},
  url         = {https://git.iem.at/davidpirro/henri}
}
```

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A Code and IR listings

This appendix collects the longer code and LLVM IR listings referenced from the body of the report. The *henri* patch for the state-variable filter described in Section 3.6 appears as Listing 17; the LLVM IR for the explicit symplectic step of the harmonic oscillator (Section 3.7) as Listing 18; and the LLVM IR for the per-sample Newton–Raphson loop solving the implicit midpoint step for the SVF as Listing 19.

Listing 17: A resonant state-variable filter with implicit integration. Patch referenced from Section 3.6.

```
def svf[2]                # [lowpass, bandpass]
def driver
def fc                    # cutoff frequency in Hz
def damp                  # damping factor (low = high Q)

driver() = in[0]
fc = 5000.0
damp = 0.05               # high-Q resonance

svf[0]'() = fc * pi2 * self[1]
svf[1]'() = -fc * pi2 * self[0] -
            2.0 * damp * fc * pi2 * self[1] +
            fc * pi2 * driver

setImplicit(svf, 0.001)  # implicit midpoint, 0.1% tol.

out[0]() = svf[0] * 0.5
```

Listing 18: LLVM IR generated by *henri* for the harmonic oscillator of Listing 3 (with $\omega = 1000$ rad/s), after optimization. Trimmed to the relevant compute body; module-level globals and platform plumbing omitted.

```
@dt_arr = external global [1 x double]
@osc_arr = external global [128 x double] ; first 2 slots: osc[0..1]

define void @compute() {
entry:
; -- Load state --
%dt = load double, ptr @dt_arr, align 8
%osc1 = load double, ptr @getelementptr inbounds
      (i8, ptr @osc_arr, i64 8), align 8 ; osc[1]
%osc0 = load double, ptr @osc_arr, align 8 ; osc[0]

; -- Stroemer-Verlet step (the three sub-steps below
;   integrate the symplectic splitting scheme of Sec. 3) --

; Half-step on osc[0]: osc[0] := osc[0] - dt * 1000 * osc[1]
%dtw = fmul fast double %dt, 1.000000e+03
%incr0a = fmul fast double %dtw, %osc1
%osc0a = fsub fast double %osc0, %incr0a

; Full step on osc[1]: osc[1] += 2 * dt * 1000 * (new osc[0])
%dt2w = fmul fast double %dt, 2.000000e+03
%incr1 = fmul fast double %dt2w, %osc0a
%osc1n = fadd fast double %incr1, %osc1

; Half-step on osc[0]: osc[0] -= dt * 1000 * (new osc[1])
%incr0b = fmul fast double %dtw, %osc1n
%osc0n = fsub fast double %osc0a, %incr0b

; -- Writeback --
store double %osc0n, ptr @osc_arr, align 8
store double %osc1n, ptr @getelementptr inbounds
      (i8, ptr @osc_arr, i64 8), align 8

ret void
}
```

Listing 19: LLVM IR generated by henri for the implicit-midpoint Newton–Raphson iteration solving the SVF of Listing 17 (trimmed; names left from LLVM’s Scalar Replacement of Aggregates pass, which breaks aggregate values into scalar registers, have been cleaned up for readability; structure preserved). Module globals and writeback of unrelated state are omitted.

```

@dt_arr = external global [1 x double]
@svf_arr = external global [128 x double] ; first 2 slots
; (parameter arrays @fc_arr, @pi2_arr, @damp_arr, @driver_arr
; loaded similarly; omitted)

define void @compute() {
entry:
; --- Load state and reusable constants ---
%dt = load double, ptr @dt_arr, align 8
%h = fmul fast double %dt, 2.000000e+00 ; h = 1/fs
%x0_n = load double, ptr @svf_arr, align 8 ; svf[0] at n
%x1_n = load double, ptr getelementptr inbounds
      (i8, ptr @svf_arr, i64 8), align 8
%fc = load double, ptr @fc_arr, align 8
%pi2 = load double, ptr @pi2_arr, align 8
%omega = fmul fast double %pi2, %fc ; 2*pi*fc
%damp = load double, ptr @damp_arr, align 8
%drv = load double, ptr @driver_arr, align 8
%wdrv = fmul fast double %omega, %drv ; omega * driver
br label %newton

newton: ; preds = %entry, %newton
; --- Loop carries: current iterate x_k and iter count ---
%x0_k = phi double [ %x0_n, %entry ], [ %x0_kp1, %newton ]
%x1_k = phi double [ %x1_n, %entry ], [ %x1_kp1, %newton ]
%iter = phi i32 [ 0, %entry ], [ %iter1, %newton ]

; --- Midpoint x_bar = (x_n + x_k) / 2 ---
%sumx = fadd fast double %x0_k, %x0_n
%midx = fmul fast double %sumx, 5.000000e-01
%sumy = fadd fast double %x1_k, %x1_n
%midy = fmul fast double %sumy, 5.000000e-01

; --- f(midpoint):
; f0 = omega * midy
; f1 = -omega*midx - 2*damp*omega*midy + omega*drv ---
%f0 = fmul fast double %omega, %midy
%npi2 = fneg fast double %pi2
%t0 = fmul fast double %midx, %npi2 ; -pi2 * midx
%m2 = fmul fast double %pi2, -2.000000e+00
%dpi2 = fmul fast double %m2, %damp ; -2*pi2*damp
%dy_t = fmul fast double %dpi2, %midy ; * midy
%sa = fadd fast double %dy_t, %t0
%sb = fmul fast double %sa, %fc ; * fc folds in
%f1 = fadd fast double %sb, %wdrv

; --- Numerical Jacobian via finite-difference (eps = 1e-8).
; Off-diagonal/diagonal entries of M = I - (h/2) df/dx ---
%hov_p = fmul fast double %dt, 1.000000e+08 ; h/(2*eps)
%hov_n = fmul fast double %dt, -1.000000e+08 ; -h/(2*eps)

; M21 column: perturb midx, recompute f1, take difference
%mxp = fsub fast double -1.000000e-08, %midx
%t1 = fmul fast double %mxp, %pi2
%sa_x = fadd fast double %dy_t, %t1
%sb_x = fmul fast double %sa_x, %fc
%j1x = fsub fast double %sb_x, %sb ; eps * df1/dx
%M21 = fmul fast double %hov_n, %j1x ; -(h/2)*df1/dx

; M12 column: perturb midy, recompute f0

```

```

%myP = fadd fast double %midy, 1.000000e-08
%fOp = fmul fast double %omega, %myP
%jOy = fsub fast double %fOp, %f0 ; eps * df0/dy
%M12 = fmul fast double %hov_n, %jOy ; -(h/2)*df0/dy

;; M22 contribution: perturb midy, recompute f1
%dy_p = fmul fast double %dpi2, %myP
%sa_y = fadd fast double %dy_p, %t0
%sb_y = fmul fast double %sa_y, %fc
%j1y = fsub fast double %sb_y, %sb ; eps * df1/dy
%hM22 = fmul fast double %hov_p, %j1y ; (h/2)*df1/dy

;; --- Residual: -R = (x_n - x_k) + h * f(midpoint) ---
%hf0 = fmul fast double %f0, %h
%nRx_p = fsub fast double %x0_n, %x0_k
%nRx = fadd fast double %nRx_p, %hf0 ; -R_x
%hf1 = fmul fast double %f1, %h
;; -R_y is constructed inline below

;; --- 2x2 Gaussian elimination on M * delta = -R ---
;; elim = M22 - M21*M12 (Schur complement)
;; gelim = -R_y - M21*(-R_x)
;; delta_y = gelim / elim
;; delta_x = -R_x - M12*delta_y
%M21M12 = fmul fast double %M12, %M21
%schur = fadd fast double %hM22, %M21M12
%elim = fsub fast double 1.000000e+00, %schur

%M21nRx = fmul fast double %nRx, %M21
%x1n_h = fadd fast double %x1_n, %hf1 ; x_n[1] + h*f1
%x1k_p = fadd fast double %x1_k, %M21nRx
%gelim = fsub fast double %x1n_h, %x1k_p
%dy = fdiv fast double %gelim, %elim ; delta_y

%M12dy = fmul fast double %M12, %dy
%dx = fsub fast double %nRx, %M12dy ; delta_x

%x0_kp1 = fadd fast double %dx, %x0_k
%x1_kp1 = fadd fast double %dy, %x1_k

;; --- Convergence test:
;; max_i |delta_i| / (|x_{k+1,i}| + 1e-15) < 1e-3 ---
%adx = call fast double @llvm.fabs.f64(double %dx)
%ax0 = call fast double @llvm.fabs.f64(double %x0_kp1)
%sc0 = fadd fast double %ax0, 1.000000e-15
%r0 = fdiv fast double %adx, %sc0
%m0 = call fast double @llvm.maxnum.f64(double %r0,
double 0.000000e+00)
%ady = call fast double @llvm.fabs.f64(double %dy)
%ax1 = call fast double @llvm.fabs.f64(double %x1_kp1)
%sc1 = fadd fast double %ax1, 1.000000e-15
%r1 = fdiv fast double %ady, %sc1
%nm = call fast double @llvm.maxnum.f64(double %r1, double %m0)

;; --- Iteration bound + branch ---
%iter1 = add nuw nsw i32 %iter, 1
%hot = fcmp fast ogt double %nm, 1.000000e-03 ; not converged
%lim = icmp ult i32 %iter, 7 ; under maxiter
%keep = and i1 %lim, %hot
br i1 %keep, label %newton, label %newton.exit

newton.exit: ; preds = %newton
;; --- Writeback ---
store double %x0_kp1, ptr @svf_arr, align 8
store double %x1_kp1, ptr @getelementptr inbounds
    
```

```
ret void          (i8, ptr @svf_arr, i64 8), align 8  
}
```